

Queer Diasporic Reading of Ghalib Shiraz Dhalla's Novel Ode to Lata

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Abstract- Ghalib Shiraz Dhalla's *Ode to Lata* (2002) is a seminal work in queer diasporic literature, exploring the intersections of migration, sexuality, and cultural identity through the life of Ali, a Queer Indian- Kenyan immigrant in Los Angeles. The proposed paper conducts Queer Diasporic reading of the novel, analyzing how Ali's displacement—both geographical and psychological—shapes his negotiation of desire, belonging, and selfhood. The novel grapples with the intersections of race, sexuality, nostalgia and gender, portraying how societal prejudices impact Ali's sense of self. Drawing on theories of Diaspora (Avtar Brah, Stuart Hall) and Queer of Color Critique (José Esteban Muñoz, Gayatri Gopinath), this study examines the way Dhalla's novel challenges heteronormative and nationalist narratives while articulating a distinctly queer South Asian diasporic subjectivity.

Keywords- Queer Diaspora, South Asian Diaspora, Migration and Identity, Queer of Color Critique, Intersectionality, Postcolonial Sexualities

I. INTRODUCTION

Ghalib Shiraz Dhalla is an American author, filmmaker, and artist. Born in Mombasa, Kenya, the author is an Indian-Kenyan queer migrant to America. His great-grandparents were Ismailis. They immigrated from India to Kenya and lived with the Indian Ismaili community. Ghalib Shiraz published his most famous work, *Dhalla Ode to Lata*, in 2002. The novelist traces the history of life over three continents—India, Kenya, and America—through three generations of a family. Dhalla's novel encourages critical reflection on the complex nature of identity and its discussion in the Diaspora and queer contexts. The term "Diaspora" refers to the dispersion or scattering of a population. The phrase 'Queer Diaspora' describes the dispersion of LGBTQ+ people, groups, and cultures outside of their original geographic or cultural contexts. The concept of diaspora acknowledges the continued linkages and feelings of identity that these scattered communities maintain with their native country or cultural origins, despite their adaptation and assimilation into new settings.

Objectives

- To attempt textual analysis of the novel *Ode to Lata*.
- To Investigate the characters' struggles with alienation, nostalgia, and the search for home in a foreign land.
- To Assess how characters negotiate dual or multiple identities across borders.
- To understand migration patterns and diasporic consciousness in the novel.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Critical analysis of the paper *Queer Diasporic Reading of Ghalib Shiraz Dhalla's novel Ode to Lata* is conducted in the light of Brah's idea of diaspora as a "contested place of belonging and unbelonging". Caught between cultural expectations (such as family and religion) and LGBT desire, the protagonist's identity struggle illustrates the complexities of diaspora as a place of both opportunity and limitation. The novel's depiction of a queer diasporic subject who defies rigid categories of "South Asianness" or "gay identity" is

consistent with Stuart Hall's and Judith Butler's idea of identity as fluid and created (as opposed to fixed). The protagonist's hardships can represent Hall's theory that identity is a "production," continually reimagined via desire, migration, and memory. José Esteban Muñoz's "Disidentification" aids in the analysis of the protagonist's manoeuvres through prevailing scripts of nation, race, belonging and desire.

III. DISCUSSION

Sexuality is considered a primary driver of queer international migration. Queer people who go abroad have the opportunity to explore their queer identities and experiences. Due to prejudice and homophobia, gay people relocate to areas that accommodate different sexual orientations and identities. They prefer countries that provide a platform to represent their true sexual orientation, allow them to come out of the 'closet', and help with identity formation.

In Ode to Lata Ghalib, Shiraz Dhalla describes the life of an Indian gay man who moves to Los Angeles to get away from the strict social conventions in his native country that forbid homosexuality. The protagonist, Ali, leaves Kenya to live a free life after coming out of his true sexual orientation. He says, "The beginning of a new life of adventure and possibility that Kenya could never offer me" (7). Ali faces challenging encounters stemming from his early years in postcolonial Kenya. He started exploring his sexuality during his kindergarten years. They both engage in homosexual behavior together. "Those days were the beginning of the discovery of my queer self. Many times, I have thought my father must have been the only one who had seen it coming and been horrified by it" (112). Numerous gay literary works depict parents becoming aware of their children's homosexuality. However, they suppress their children's sexual orientation and endeavor to convert their homosexuality into heterosexuality. The homophobic situation originates within the household of a queer individual, compelling them to hide their sexual orientation from their parents, relatives, and the wider community. He has a

domineering mother who exercises control and authority. She exposes Ali to a consistent intake of Hindi cinema, and Bollywood tunes exert a significant influence on their miserable lives.

Ali's cultural history and the prevailing taboo against homosexuality in South Asian communities contribute to his feelings of humiliation and loneliness. Because he is bisexual, he also faces challenges adhering to conventional gender standards and expectations. His mother casts a shadow over his existence, serving as a constant reminder of the expectations placed upon him by his "native community." She strongly adheres to the Indian value system. She has the belief that it is crucial to get into matrimony, establish a family, and have permanent residence. Initially, Ali faces the difficulty of hiding his sexual orientation in his hometown of Mombasa, Kenya. After observing the oppression faced by many of his gay friends because of their sexual orientation, as well as their choice to enter into heterosexual marriages, create families, and establish a stable lifestyle, he chose to move to Los Angeles. His decision to relocate to the United States is a deliberate effort to create his independent existence, unburdened by the societal pressure to get married and raise family.

Ali successfully manages both a full-time job and a vibrant social life. He works as a banker during the day and frequents clubs in Los Angeles at night. The book intertwines Ali's narrative with the disintegration of his parents' ill-fated marriage and the celebrated Bollywood vocalist Lata Mangeshkar, widely recognized as the 'Diva' of Indian film music. Lata's excessively sentimental song emphasizes their anguished lives, motivating them to pursue love in the middle of disorder and happiness. Ali's identification with Bollywood songs highlights his gay subjectivity, emphasizing the queer appropriation of a dominant cultural manifestation. The songs hold particular importance within LGBT subcultures as they provide a means for expressing nonconventional or marginalized relationships. Bollywood also plays a crucial role in preserving the connection between the Indian queer diaspora and their home country. Ali and his South Asian queer friends, including Indians and others, are nostalgic

for their early years under the influence of Bollywood music. They establish an emotional connection with their country of origin. Bollywood songs are a technique for seeking solace and overcoming the feelings of loneliness and alienation that people encounter in their adopted country. Ali has a strong preference for Bollywood music, which, he asserts, evokes feelings of nostalgia and a sense of belonging. "Lata, the celestial voice I encountered in every Hindi film during my childhood, adds," he says (11), "One of Lata Mangeshkar's songs, 'Inhi logo ne', is like a litmus paper that makes Indian parents discover their children's homosexuality (50). Not only the Indian queer diaspora, but also the wider Indian diaspora, consider Bollywood to be an integral part of their lives, providing a respite from the challenges they face back home. Because they feel at home in a foreign land, they listen to Bollywood songs.

Ode to Lata is highly acclaimed for its various elements that question established norms of home and traditional ideas of the Diaspora, particularly from a heteronormative standpoint. The subjectivity of queer individuals from South Asia living in diaspora challenges the problematic notion that same-sex desire originates from the home. Considering the conventional notions of race and gender-based hierarchies, Ali's queerness becomes a form of advantage or benefit. Gayatri Gopinath's concept of the queer Diasporic frame of analysis describes home as a national, communal, or domestic space that is not based on concepts of blood, purity, authenticity, or patrilineal descent. Through the integration of knowledge from diaspora studies and queer theory, this text explores the relationship between diasporic forms and queer cultural practices. It emphasizes the significance of the queer diasporic subject in discussions about queerness, diaspora, race, and home. This method seeks to integrate queer cultural practices into narratives of diaspora, focusing on themes of origin, history, and identity. By doing so, it aims to challenge the hierarchical structures that marginalize non-white queer individuals.

Ali encounters instances of racism, bigotry, exclusion, and degradation among the LGBT community in Los Angeles, United States. He forms connections with the LGBTQ+ community in South Asia, encompassing those from Pakistan and Sri Lanka who identify as Indians. He faces numerous challenges within this community. As a result, he comes to the conclusion that he is unable to obtain acceptance in any place. Ali recounts his grandfather's emigration from India to Kenya. Furthermore, he explores the enduring impact of colonialism and elucidates his family's choice to move to Africa. He experiences nostalgia for his homeland, Kenya, after relocating to Los Angeles. Richard, Ali's estranged romantic partner, reflects Ali's sense of grief and longing for home. Ali strives to cultivate his American identity and establish a sense of belonging by organizing his life around the rhythms and themes of American dramas such as *Melrose Place*.

However, the continuous outbursts of his Kenyan heritage and his Indian upbringing evoke in him a feeling of deprivation, longing, and sadness. Dhalla establishes a strong correlation between queer longing and the issues of migration and identity by introducing the central theme of Ali's intense love for Richard at the outset of the narrative. Unlike heterosexual individuals, who frequently recall their childhood and other experiences in their home country, most gay diaspora inhabitants have no desire to return, even if they feel a longing for their natal land. Ali says, "Going home is no longer an option. Was it ever?" (14). Even though he is aware that in Kenya his sexual orientation is not acceptable, Ali still refers to Kenya as his home: "Even after all these years, I still refer to Kenya as 'home.'" (113)

The protagonist of Dhalla's book rewrites traditional depictions of home in Diasporic imagination. In her analysis of the diaspora concept in *Thinking through the Concept of Diaspora*, Avtar Brah emphasizes the diasporic imagination's longing, for he observes that "home" as a mythical site of yearning in Diasporic Discourses. Parallel to this, Salman Rushdie asserts in his book *Imaginary Homeland* that the need to recover the past

frequently prompts writers to invent stories about imagined homelands. Ali's idealized depiction of Richard in Kenya mirrors his fluctuating, redeeming perspective of Kenya, the nation he yearns to escape from during his stay. The creation of the fictitious Kenyan homeland serves as an example of a mnemonic technique that becomes comparable to and reminiscent of Ali's desire for Richard. Kenya appears to be an imagined place that Ali returns to as he creates fiction about his past, even as the longing for Richard drives the main plot of the novel. For Ali, at the start of the book, the picture of the Kenyan flag with its vibrant red and green colors fades in comparison to the American flag's unbreakable promise of goodwill. Kenya, however, turns out to be a fabrication that, like Richard, develops only inside the boundaries of his imagined home as the story goes on. Richard's deodorant smells remarkably like the distinctive Kenyan perfume that Ali longs for in his dreams, which is how Ali feels connected to Richard. His imaginary reconstructions of the Kenyan railway and his connection to it illustrate his yearning for Kenya. Ali's need for Kenya was never satisfied by moving to Los Angeles, just as all of his sexual encounters with others failed to satisfy his desire for Richard.

Despite his geographic freedom, the memories of the house he left behind forever bind Ali. He continues to ride the railroad in his fantasies. Likewise, he is only able to relate to the Kenyan delicacies that his mother provides him through an unrealistic framework. The romance between Richard and Ali, which ended six years ago, represents a sentimental past, much like Kenya. Ali recreates a version of Richard that is more like the imagined Richard than the actual Richard because of his need for the absent lover. Ali is aware of his hunger and his tendency to steal from others, even when Richard is physically present with him. "Richard's adultery prompts Ali to reconstruct a romanticized past that idolizes Richard as the pinnacle of "aesthetic perfection." (31) As he goes to visit Richard in the hospital, he realizes that his perception of him is a fabrication. As he observes, "Six years had gone by, and I was still standing at his bedside in some hospital because he might

have fucked his life away, while I had spent nights with little more than my fantasies of him" (51-52).

Lesbian and gay discourses at home generally view queerness as something to abandon in order to embrace emancipated queer sexuality. Hence, migration (away from home) becomes a crucial aspect of queerness. We might see Ali's relocation to Los Angeles as departure from the West and shift towards an LGBTQ-progressive culture. The Los Angeles gay bar and endless sexual encounter subculture eloquently express Ali's suppressed queer identity. In her book *Impossible Desires*, Gopinath provides a detailed explanation of the role of home in queer Diasporic texts. She clarifies: By combining discourses on class, sexuality, and ethnic identity, queer diasporic literature creates "home" locations that are perpetually and already torn apart. By making both the object of desire and pleasure in a nostalgic diasporic imagination, they stake claim to both the home place and the country. In these books, the heteronormative home unintentionally fosters homoeroticism. (15)

Dhalla's novel provides a novel viewpoint on the subjective experiences of male LGBT individuals living in diaspora, emphasizing the simultaneous presence of different types of exclusion alongside conflicting feelings of attachment and repulsion towards their country of origin. This adds further subtleties to the solitary interpretations of diasporic identities, which stress the physically linear account of displacement over alternative forms of association. Furthermore, cultural artifacts that act as a connection between the dispersed community and non-heteronormative identities, such as Bollywood, also reinforce the prevailing standards of racial stratification.

Queer Indian Americans frequently experience conflict between their ethno-religious identity and their distinct sexual orientation. In order to regain the geographical center, he lost in Kenya, Ali constructed his residence in the United States. Nevertheless, adopting a diasporic framework imbues his American residency with a fresh significance, enabling the cultivation of his Indian identity. Consequently, the gay individual who is

part of the diaspora chooses to incorporate Islamic rituals into his experience, aligning them with religious practices. Unlike the typical association of a home with a specific location, the novel presents it as a cultural creation. He envisions himself as being patient, forgiving, and potentially capable of preventing himself from straying again, similar to his mother.

Dhalla says that the mother-son bond is the primary source of attachment among the diaspora. The proposed feminine subject position challenges the notion of fixed gender roles, which prescribes those adult males should align themselves with masculine role models. Ali has a large number of friends who have engaged in gay behavior until marriage. Ali struggles to comprehend why all gay men are transitioning to heterosexuality, "Ali wonders who made the right choice. Is it his friends who chose to hide their sexuality from society and marry a girl, and after marriage, who will continue their homosexual acts and cheat their wives? Or is it he who chose to come out and reveal his sexuality to his mother and fought with her for his sexuality and his gay identity?" (75). Ironically, the book strengthens male power over the female body by allowing queer diasporic connections with the oppressed female character. The gorgeous proportions of Meena Kumari and Helen obscure the consequences of using women's bodies for male gratification. Ali presents his mother as the ideal Indian mother, downplaying her sexuality, and portrays his father as an engaged sexual partner. For Ali, she serves as a model of the Mother India character, giving her life to further the common good. He saw her as the perfect Indian mother, which made her feel guilty for not being able to have grandkids. Ali's Indian lesbian companion, Farida, is the only other woman in the book besides his mother. The book does not fully explore Farida's lesbian identity, despite her role as the organizer of the gay South Asian support organization SAATH (togetherness).

Migration (away from home) is a key component of queerness, and in lesbian and gay discourses, home usually operates against queerness. This design portrays Kenya as the "home" of forced

heteronormativity, contrasting with Ali's relocation to Los Angeles. But Ali's quick trip back to Kenya and his ongoing yearning for the past complicate any tidy analysis of "home" as a queer-suppressive place. Gopinath offers a clarifying explanation of the role of home in literature on the LGBT diaspora. She clarifies,

The resignification of 'home' within a queer diasporic imaginary makes three crucial interventions: first, it forcefully repudiates the elision of queer subjects from national and diasporic memory; second, it denies their function as a threat to family, community, or nation; and third, it refuses to position queer subjects as alien, inauthentic, and perennially outside the confines of these entities. (15)

The conclusion of the novel portrays Ali as the melancholic hero of Bollywood cinema, isolated despite his profound yearning for love. But two significant occasions towards the end of *Ode to Lata* indicate a departure from the story's central theme of desire. Immediately following Ali's departure, the Saath support organization announced that "a new, vibrant young woman who had just emigrated from India took over the post of South Asian coordinator" (284). The concealed sexist stance of Ali throughout the narrative challenges the novel's attempt to combat such prejudice by appointing the "vibrant young woman" to his position. Ali decides to accept the group offer and undergoes an HIV test. His affirmation that he is "perhaps alone, but not bitter" supports this constructive action, which aligns with his eventual release from his love for Richard. "Never take offense. I want to live; thus, I want to have a desire for as long as I live" (284). These instances highlight the many ways in which Ali deals with Richard's absence, his longing for home, and his "gradually disappearing" family (283).

Sum up

The protagonist's engagement with homeland—whether through nostalgia, music, or language—highlights the enduring psychological and emotional ties to the past, even as they forge new meanings in their adopted spaces. The novel also

critiques monolithic notions of belonging, suggesting that diasporic identity is an ongoing process rather than a fixed state. Ali learns that bigotry and rejection of South Asians exist in America, despite its outward appearance. While it does allow for sexual expression, it does not accept black individuals. Ali discovers that he never imagined living a life full of rejection and fleeting happiness after moving to Los Angeles. He desired a life of acceptance and, above all, a sense of belonging that he was unable to find in Los Angeles. He claims that if the upheaval in Kenya had not compelled him to uphold social norms, he would never have moved to Los Angeles.

IV. CONCLUSION

Ghalib Shiraz Dhalla's *Ode to Lata* offers a vital contribution to queer diasporic literature, foregrounding the complex interplay of migration, sexuality, race, and memory in shaping diasporic queer subjectivity. Through Ali's fragmented identity and his constant negotiation between cultural expectations, racialized desire, and queer longing, the novel dismantles dominant narratives of belonging rooted in heteronormativity and nationalism. Rather than offering a resolution or return to a fixed home, *Ode to Lata* embraces dislocation as a generative space from which alternative modes of identity and desire can emerge.

By situating the novel within the frameworks of diaspora theory (Avtar Brah, Stuart Hall) and queer of color critique (José Esteban Muñoz, Gayatri Gopinath), this paper has shown how Dhalla's work resists linear trajectories of assimilation or integration. Instead, it articulates a fluid, affective queer diasporic sensibility that holds space for contradiction, multiplicity, and longing. *Ode to Lata* ultimately asserts that queer South Asian diasporic lives cannot be understood through singular lenses but must be read through the intersections of race, gender, sexuality, and displacement—where identity is not static but constantly negotiated, imagined, and reimagined across borders.

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